

Statistical Characteristics of Distribution of Radiation-Induced Defects under Random Generation

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Abstract : We consider fluctuations of defects density taking into account their interaction. Stochastic field of displacement generation rate gives random defect distribution. We determinate statistical characteristics (mean and dispersion) of random field of point defect distribution as function of defect generation parameters, temperature and properties of irradiated crystal.

Keywords : irradiation, primary defects, interaction, fluctuations

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